

Geospatial Monitoring of Urban Growth and Vegetation Destruction in Gusau City, Zamfara State

^{*1}Kabiru A. and ¹Muhammad S. K.

¹*Department of Geography, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State

*Correspondence: akabiru11@gmail.com; +2347063481767

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Abstract

Urban areas in developing countries are significantly experiencing an unprecedented increase in built-up areas often in an uncoordinated manner. Over the last two decades, the rapid urban growth of Gusau city has attracted significant attention from the governments, policy makers and researchers. This work was aimed at analyzing the influence of urban growth in Gusau city on the Land Use Land Cover (LULC) changes and proposes solutions to address urbanization challenges. The geospatial methods used were remote sensing and geographic information systems. Whereas, the survey techniques comprises of in-depth interview and direct observation across the five political Wards in Gusau city, as well as relevant ministries in the State. Furthermore, the analysis further shows that urban expansion in the city was triggered mainly by political, socio-economic, and demographic factors. The results revealed that, built-up areas increased from a minimum of 6.13 km² in 1999 to 12.37 km² in 2006, with net 6.24 km² (between 1999 and 2006). Similarly, the built-up areas were also found to have continuously increased to 18.31 km² in the 2012 and 19.82 km² in 2018. It is concluded that, the city has significantly grown both horizontally and vertically in about 20 years from the date of state creation in the 1996. And that it is recommended that the adoption of geospatial techniques in monitoring of urban growth for better decision making should be considered and that, sound and efficient urban policies guided by socioeconomic planning and sustainability are the panacea to the current urbanization problems.

Keywords: GIS, LULC Monitoring, Remote sensing, Urban Growth, Urbanization

1.0 Introduction

Recently, urbanization has been the major topic of scientific discourse among the academics, policy spaces and environmental change research. Cities have undergone rapid expansion and transformation as a consequence of human population growth and other anthropogenic factors [9]. Globally, 4 billion people were estimated to have inhabited urban areas, which accounts for more than half of the global population [22]. This trend is projected to hit 8 billion people by the year 2050, in which urban population contributes nearly 80% of the global Gross Domestic Products (GDP) [25, 23]. Urbanization phenomenon occurs not only in developing states, but also advanced nations. However, urban expansions in the developing nations, such as in Asian and African cities are basically due to either natural population growth or rural-urban migrations [21]. Urbanization facilitates economic productivity

mainly because of cheap labour, abundant market and industrialization as seen in China and India, but the ecological footprints associated with it has an important environmental concern. The United Nation Center for Trade Development [24] reveals that increase in impervious surfaces associated with urban land conversion led to the decrease infiltration and high surface runoff. Importantly, most urban expansion occurs on fertile agricultural lands or forests which are generally associated with increased energy use and increased pollution. This growth was believed to have caused more harm than good to the urban populace in terms of good health, education, housing, sanitation, transport, and culture.

A considerable body of literature has evolved to explain urban forms, such as leapfrog, expansion, infilling and edge expansion [2, 18, 25]. More recently, urbanization and consequential expansion of urban areas have become the central focus of

development agenda, which continues to attract considerable interests from across the globe. For instance, [19, 17] focused majorly on the environmental and social implication of urban growth in the United State. Similarly, [5,20] and [16] quantitatively analyses the drivers of urban expansion in Chinese cities. In Sub-Saharan Africa including Nigeria, it is crucial to study urban growth and the impacts of associated factors including rapid population growth and rural-urban migration on land cover transformation and overall development.

Although, most studies in the African continent focused on the evaluation of nexus between urbanization and agriculture, some have particularly focused on urban planning and infrastructural growth [15, 14]. In Nigeria, Gusau city inclusive, the problems associated with land cover transformation persist and the new other issues have emerged, which include but not limited to development of shanty and ghetto areas, destruction of agricultural lands and the general destruction of vegetation and ecosystems [7]. This paper aimed at assessing the rate and nature of urban growth in Gusau city using GIS technologies. The specific objectives were to identify the major factors influencing urban growth, as well as to measure the extent of the growth across the periods (1999-2018) of the study.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

Gusau is the administrative capital of Zamfara State, Nigeria, located between Latitude

12°13'N to 12°18'N and Longitude 6°29'E to 6°45'E, at an elevation of 451m above the sea level (figure 1). The city shares boarder with Kwatarkwashi to the east, Rawayya to the north, Wanke to the south and Bungudu to the west. In 2006, Gusau had a population of 383,162 people and an estimated 682,700 inhabitants in 2022, from its annual growth rate of 2.7% National Population Commission [13].

The climate of Gusau is a typical semiarid/arid climate type controlled by the northerly wet and south moving dry continental air masses, resulting in two alternate rainy and dry seasons respectively [11]. The wet air from the south results in five months rainy season (June to October), while the dust laden dry air mass from the Sahara desert results in three (3) months of Harmattan cold season, (December to February) in the area[11]. Similarly, the Gusau city receives an average annual precipitation of about 868mm and experience an average temperature of 26.3⁰Annually [10]. The geology of the area is typically of Northern plain, plains of Hausa land, underlain by basement complex rocks of Precambrian era. Granite and gneiss are the common extrusion in the area [10]. The city falls within Sudan savannah vegetation zone characterized by short grasses and scattered thorny trees and locust bean type. The area is drained by River Sokoto which originated from Funtua highland among other minor streams and tributaries.

Figure 1: Map of the Study Area **Source:** GIS Laboratory, Geography Department, BUK (2019)

1.2 Satellite imagery

The satellite imagery was downloaded freely from the website of the United State Geological Survey (USGS) through the URL (www.usgs.gov). The 1999, 2006, 2012 and 2018 Landsat imageries with high spatial resolution of 30 Meters (M), projected

to World Geodetic System (WGS) 84 and Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) Zone 45 (Table 1). The analysis period covers 1999 to 2018 with 6 years interval. The land cover map produced from the imagery served as input to the change detection analysis [3, 20].

Table 1: Characteristics of Landsat Imageries used in the Research

SN	Sensor	Date of acquisition	Spatial resolution	Source	Path/Raw
1	Landsat7	07/10/1999	30M	USGS website	190/52
2	Landsat7	07/10/2006	30M	USGS website	190/52
3	Landsat7	07/10/2012	30M	USGS website	190/52
4	Landsat8	08/10/2018	30M	USGS website	190/52

1.3 Interviews and observations (Ground-truth data)

The interview interviews with urban planning experts from Zamfara state Urban and Regional Planning Board was conducted and the local experts were also interviewed to obtain the information on the key driving factors of urban growth in Gusau city. Furthermore, direct observations were carried out to verify training sites for land use/Land cover classification using Global Positioning System (GPS) and the coordinates were recorded and the points were visited to identify and confirm the nature of the land in the city.

1.4 Other dataset

Vector dataset was obtained from the Department of Geography, Bayero University Kano to curve out the required areal dimension for the land cover maps. The statistical data comprising the population data of the city for the years 2010 and 2016 were obtained from the website of the National Population Commission [13]

2.0 Data Analysis

The satellite imageries were processed in GIS environment using Arc GIS 10.6.0 software. The imageries were first pre-processed, stacked and subset. The classification was carried out using maximum likelihood supervised classification algorithm. The training sites were selected based on the researcher's familiarity with the study area [4, 12]. For land use/land cover mapping, the study area was divided into built-up and non-built-up

areas. The non-built-up areas comprise of green and bare land areas, while the built-up areas include all other uses: commercial, residential areas, roads, and administrative structures. Although, urban areas are characterized by the dominance of built-up areas, the land use/land cover change were computed to detect the land cover changes in the area and how it was changing over time. However, the results of interviews data were used to explain some of the empirical findings.

3.0 Result and Discussions

3.1 Spatial Expansion of Gusau City from 1999-2018

The 1999 is a baseline period for this study, built-up area covered an area of 6.13 Km² (13.12%) of the study area (Figure 2 and Table 2). In this year, the built-up areas were mostly located in the south-eastern and south-central parts of Gusau city. Those are areas within old Gusau city comprised of Kanwuri, Tsohuwar Kasuwa, Sabon-Fege, Kanteen Daji, GRA, and Sabon-Gari. Other notable built-up areas include Mortgage, Tudun-Wada, the CBD, Samuru Damba and Mareri. In the north-west and the western parts of the city, there are however, scattered built-up areas in Gada-biyu, Janyau, Abarma, Farkuwa, Madidi and NNPC Depot (Figure 2). However, the result showed that in 1999, Gusau city has a compact type of settlement typified by a mixture of residential, commercial, and institutional land uses (Government house, Hospital, Schools and other Government agencies) with some exception in Kanteen-Daji and the Gusau industrial district.

Figure 2: Land Use/Land Cover Map of Gusau City in 1999

Table 2: Land Use and Land Cover extent of Gusau in 1999

SN	Land use types	Area (km ²)	Area percentage
1	Built-up areas	6.13	13.12
2	Bare lands	15.86	34.01
3	Vegetation	22.84	48.92
4	Water bodies	1.89	4.001
Total		46.64	100.00

The vegetation cover in 1999 occupied an area of 22.48km² (48.92%) of the study area (Table 1). The dense vegetation cover in the western part of the city, Samuru and Damba areas could have been the result of tree plantation projects of 1940s and 50s during which all the industries in the city were operational.

In 1999 Gusau city was 3 years old of being Zamfara state capital and the first year of civilian rule. The analysis result of the baseline period indicates that the built-up areas were still in the early stage of growth with a prospect of major expansion due to anticipated development. The housing and infrastructural demand characterized

emerging city like Gusau at this period under scores their potential for future growth.

3.2 The Spatial Extent of Gusau City in 2006

By 2006, the built-up areas have increased from 6.3Km in 1999 to 14.37km² (from 6.3 km) (30.88%) of the total land area of the city (Figure 3 and Table 3), indicating an increased by 17.8% in 7 years. However, bare land has significantly reduced to 9.31km² in 2006. This could have been due to expansion in the built-up areas as a result of human population growth. Similarly, although it has slightly reduced by 2.2% compared to 1999, vegetation cover was still the dominant land use in 2006 in the study area.

Figure 3: Land Use/Land Cover Map of Gusau in 2006

The decrease in the vegetal cover in 2006 was due to basic demographic and economic factors. For instance, the population of Gusau city grew up from 259,339 people in 1999 to 383,712 in 2006 [13]. The increase in human population directly led

to the increased demand for crop land and, residential spaces and the rapid conversion of vegetation cover and bare land into agricultural areas [1].

Table 3: Land Use and Land Cover extent of Gusau in 2006

SN	Land use types	Area (km ²)	Area percentage
1	Built-up areas	14.37	30.88
2	Bare lands	9.31	19.94
3	Vegetation	21.76	46.71
4	Water bodies	1.15	2.47
Total		46.59	100.00

3.3 The Spatial Extent of Gusau City in 2012

Further analysis shows that, Gusau urban land use has significantly expanded in 2012 (18.31 Km) from 14.37 km² in 2006. The rapid expansion of

built-up areas was observed particularly around Tsunami Layout, an area allocated to the victims of Gusau flood disaster of 2006/2007 (Figure 4 and Table 5).

Figure 4: Land Use/ Land Cover Map of Gusau city In 2012

Moreover, the growth observed during this period were mainly due to construction of housing estate and government offices at different locations in

Gusau city by the Zamfara State Government to boost infrastructural development and address housing demand (Table 5).

Table 4: Housing Estate Constructed in Gusau city between 2006 and 2012.

SN	Name of the estate	Number of Housing Units	Location
1	Commissioners Quarters	60	Bypass
2	GidanDawa housing	300	Gada-biyu
3	Alasawa/Daza Estate	500	Janyau
4	RijiyarGabas Phase I & II	100	Rijiyar Gabas
5	Damba Quarters	200	Damba

The analysis also reveals a decrease in bare land areas in 2012 compared to 2006 from 9.31km² to 6.75km² (14.48%) of the land area respectively (Figure 4 and Table 5). Changes in the vegetal cover were marginal during this period, only about 1.42km². This could have been because of the

large-scale developments targeted at the established across city spaces and conversion of the existing space into developmental facilities. For instance, the conversion of Ali Akilu convocation square into Yariman Bakura Specialist Hospital which sites at the city center.

Table 5: Land Use and Land Cover extent of Gusau in 2012

SN	Land use types	Area (km ²)	Area percentage
1	Built-up areas	18.31	39.32
2	Bare land	6.75	14.48
3	Vegetation	20.34	43.65
4	Water bodies	1.19	2.55
Total		46.59	100.00

3.4 The Spatial Extent of Gusau City in 2018

In 2018, the built-up area of the city has increased to 19.82 Km², an increase of about 3.22 Km² compared to 2012 (Figure 5 and Table 6). This expansion was generally observed in all parts of the city although this is a small change compared to 2006 and 2012, which could be due to the focus of infrastructural development ranging from housing and to roads construction and provision of other basic needs like water and electricity to the city. Nonetheless, few federal and states institutions

were constructed during this period such as Federal University Gusau, Military formations to fight banditry in the state as well as massive migration in the city due to security situations in the villages.

On the other hand, bare land had experienced the highest rate of decrease from 6.75 Km² in 2012 to 3.56 Km² (7.64% in 2018). The decrease were mainly due to the expansion in built-up areas.

Figure 5: Land Use/ Land Cover Map of Gusau City In 2018

The vegetation cover also shows a slight increase as presented by the analysis, from 20.34 km² in 2012 to (21.43 Km² in 2018). The increase in vegetation was basically due to conversion of bare land areas to gardens and cropland areas, the

increase in the size of crop land was majorly triggered by the conversion of bare lands areas into irrigation fields and gardens purposely to provide more food that would support the growing human population.

Table 6: Land Use and Land Cover extent of Gusau in 2018

SN	Land use types	Area (km ²)	Area percentage
1	Built-up Areas	19.82	42.54
2	Bare Land	3.56	7.54
3	Vegetation	21.43	46.00
4	Water bodies	1.78	3.82
5	Total	46.59	100.00

Moreover, water bodies in 2018, shows an increase of a total area of 1.78 Km² (3.82%) as against 1.19 Km² in 2012 (Table 7). This increase in the volume of water bodies were due to the increase demands for construction materials (such as sand and gravels) which usually comes from the river and channels. The continuous removal of these construction materials have gradually caused the increased expansion of water bodies in the area.

3.5 Spatial Pattern of urban growth (Infill and Expansion)

The results show that the spatial pattern of land transformation of Gusau city during 1999–2005, 2006–2012, 2013–2018. During 1999–2005 infill development was relatively low with only 2.04Km² of vacant land in the city was subjected to infill, which amounted to only 4.4% of total urban growth. Conversely, 95.6% of urban growth occurred on the fringes of the city as expansion, mainly along the three major transportation corridors, around the city periphery and arterial roads in three angles of the city, i.e. Eastern, Northern and Southern directions. During 2006–2012, large areas along the newly established residential areas and around existing urban peripheries were converted to urban use. Infill development increased to 9.15 Km², about (19.66%) of total urban growth, while 80% of land around the city periphery was urbanized through expansion. Whereas, during 2013–2018, both infill and expansion became more prominent with a conversion of 15.1 Km² vacant land in existing built-up areas as infill and 31.49 km² as expansion respectively.

4.0 Factors influencing Urban Growth in Gusau City

The rapid growth of Gusau city and its peri-urban areas are not without causes and consequences. An assessment of related researches has clearly pointed out the paramount influence of multiple driving factors in determining urban growth in the study area. Therefore, this section of the paper focused on the examination of factors responsible for urban growth in Gusau city. These factors according to the finding of this research include basically: the political, administrative, economic and social factors.

The finding of this study reveals that, the creation of Zamfara State and the emergence of Gusau as a state capital in year 1996 was the most fundamental political factor that encouraged the

rapid growth and expansion of the city. Similarly, the research found that, this development directly led to the transformation of Gusau to a higher degree as a complex urban center. Another most important aspect of politics in this regard was the government desire to create and provide suitable environment to accommodate high profile civil servants, the foreign expatriate and local business men and women trooping into the city. Interview with concern authorities confirmed that, this was the most pressing challenge that posed the state government to swing into action and began the construction new urban structures in order to provide offices for the activities of government and residential accommodation for the state civil servants [1].

“State creation in the year 1996 was an important stride in the development of Gusau town. It gave birth to the emergence of the town to assume the status of state capital. This attracted large wave of native and non-native migrants from all over the country and beyond. So also, the provision of basic infrastructural facilities such as education, health and finance, offers job opportunities and new ground for investment. However, various national and foreign companies are now in the state to acquire contracts with the state government which also create more employment to the people in the town as well as revenue to Government, we thank God”

The research further reveals that, Zamfara State Government policies on reclassification of rural areas into urban and the resettlements of families affected by the project establishment at across the city, has contributed immensely to the rapid expansion of the city. Reclassification of rural communities surrounding Gusau city have also led to the inclusion of many villages into the metropolitan area of the city.

According to [1], the development of infrastructures and basic amenities in Gusau city which cut across educational institutions, government offices, residential accommodations, establishment of layouts, provision and extension of township road and water supply scheme among others.

“About 12 sets of housing estates were constructed by the state government in a period of just 15years from 1999 to 2013. These include Damba Housing estate, Abdussalam Abubakar 100 units, Gidan Dawa Housing Estate, Mikab Housing Estate, Mareri Housing Estate, Igala Quarters, and

Commissioners/Legislative Quarters among others”.

However, the proliferation of commercial and industrial activities in Gusau city were said to have been reinvigorated, since the establishment of industrial plans which took place in 1923. According the finding of this research from the historical archives, it was found that the production and trading of various agricultural and manufactured products were the major commercial activities taking place in Gusau city alongside other foreign products being brought into the city [6, 8]. More so, with the phenomenon of state creation, governments of Zamfara state have in various attempts introduced policies and programs aimed at improving commercial activities in the state through the award of start-up capital to the businessmen and farmers across the state [11].

Furthermore, the introduction of Islamic Shari'ah system in Zamfara state in the year 2000 was found to have accelerated the process of urbanization, hence urban expansion in Gusau city. This is because the state government under the leadership of the former governor, Ahmad Yariman Bakura had established various ministries and agencies responsible for managing the Islamic affairs in the state. According to one respondent, many Nigerians and non-Nigerians have migrated to the city whom were allured by the provisions of the Shari'ah which includes; Justice to all, peace and harmony among different religious groups and tribe.

“Also Another Important Factor That Has Attracted Many People Into This Town Was The Introduction of Shari'ah Legal System By The Administration Of Yariman Bakura In The Year 2000” “In addition, various ministries and agencies were established for the consolidation of the principles of Shari'ah system which include: Zakat and Endowment Board, Ministry for Religious Affair, Zamfara State Hisbah Commission, and Directorate for Qur'anic Schools, among others” (interview with Director Ministry of Works and transport, 2019).

Other finding from interviews also reveals that, since the last decade, Zamfara state is confronted by serious security challenges promoted by the activities of banditry, kidnapping and cattle rustling among other criminal activities. These phenomena have led to the out-migration of many rural families who fled their communities to find shelters in the city. This situation has caused the

transformation in the demographics of the city as a result of large volume of migrants coming into the city, in which many of the displaced families resolved in establishing their own residential structures in the city. Whereas, some of them moved back to their communities as normalcy is restored in their respective communities (Interview, 2020). Likewise, security challenge in Zamfara state have led to the establishment of various security facilities and upgrading of many with modern equipment in the city ranging from Army Barracks, Polices Stations And Air Force Base among others.

5.0 Conclusion

This research demonstrates the ability of geospatial techniques in the study of urban growth and vegetation destruction. The results obtained revealed a rapid and continuous development in the build-up areas of Gusau city particularly during the last twenty years. Similarly, the research established that, the most influential forces responsible for the rapid growth in Gusau city are basically, political, demographic, and socioeconomic factors, with creation of Zamfara state being the paramount.

6.0 Recommendations

Owing to the continual spatial and demographic increase in urban growth the following are recommended:

- i.** There is need for a regular monitoring of urban growth and development in the study area for better decision making.
- ii.** The relevant authorities and stakeholders such as: Directorate for Housing and Urban Development, Zamfara State Urban and Regional Planning Board, Ministry for works and transport and land developer to ensure strict adherence to land use and planning regulations.
- iii.** Government should encourage researchers on urban-related issues with socio-economic impacts in the study area for a more in-depth understanding of the dynamics of urbanization.
- iv.** Environmentalist in the state should initiate an environmental protection campaign against the perils poor planning on social and economic wellbeing of the people in the city.

7.0 References

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